

HOW TO IMPROVE SPEAKING SKILLS

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Abstract: The article discusses the importance of how to develop speaking skills in English. The article also analyzes the positions of various ways and methods aimed at developing the oral speech. Some challenges in mastering the skill of speaking that arise in the classroom of the English language are considered. We will see what the role of instructor so as to progress the learner's skills the features of oral communication that need to be improved and which strategies can be used to overcome the problems. Modern technology is also seen as ways of assisting students to advance language skills. Video, podcasts, internet are the best tools to teach speaking skills. So, speaking is one of the crucial means of communication.

Key words: speaking skills, oral communication, teaching strategies, methods, modern technology.

Ancy foreign language has its own challenges. Difficulties in mastering speaking skills arise for a number of objective and subjective causes. Firstly, objective one, we mean the insufficient material and technical equipment of lessons, the overload of the student collective, which reduces the time of oral communication allotted to educational and methodological complex for conducting reading classes. Secondly, subjective reasons, we think about the student's psychological and emotional state (self-doubt, low self-esteem, fear of making mistakes, etc.); a small amount of knowledge in academic disciplines such as regional studies, cultural studies, linguistics; limited vocabulary and inability to use it as active vocabulary is considered.

Moreover, some students agreed that they could speak on a given topic for a limited duration, while more than half did not agree in this connection. Some students were scolded by their teachers for speaking incorrectly in English but more than half did not think so. Some of the students could not speak in the classrooms of English because of the fears of their teachers. Another important point to be added over here was that maximum number of the students was shy because of the fear that their class fellows would laugh at them. According to the data, some students knew how to speak correctly. Another part of students responded that their teachers did

not speak English most of the time in the classes of English. Different activities such as seminars, group discussions and debates, competitions were not regularly arranged to develop the group.

Improving the speaking ability, you should more stress on the quality of books at the basic level, enough time given to speaking and phonetic drills of students, no scolding but provision of friendly environment, making practical and applicable strategies by teachers for learners while speaking most of time in English, develop boldness and confidence in students for asking questions from their teachers no overcrowded classes, awards and motivation for students, the role of media such as listening to CNN and BBC, inclusion of viva voce in the examination system at various levels for checking the competence of the candidates, up to-date and constant training of teachers, arranging various activities and balance in the courses with respect to literature and language should be there to provide opportunities to improve the language competency of students.

There some ways to improve speaking skills:

1. Listening

There are many resources available to you to listen to for free. Start with short English clips or videos: pick your favorite English TV show or YouTube channel. Listen to a clip and notice carefully what the characters are saying. Repeat any dialogues or phrases that interest you. Replay the same clip until you understand each word. You could also turn on the subtitles or look at the transcript of the video if available and practice saying the dialogues with the characters.

2. Audio book

Another way to improve your listening and speaking is by listening to audio books. Audio books have become very popular over the past couple of years. They are great for people who have no time to invest in reading books. They are also a wonderful way to perfect your pronunciation. Try to listen to a portion of the text, pause the audio, and read aloud to practice saying the words yourself.

3. Reading

Reading is yet another important skill to have when learning a language. Whether you prefer a novel or an article, reading a few minutes every day will help you to acquire new vocabulary.

The most common reason why people hesitate with reading is that it takes quite a lot of time to read a book from start to finish. However, when learning English, reading even for a few minutes is greatly beneficial. Short articles or notes in English are great for this. They only take a few minutes to read and are quite easy to find.

4. Imitating

It will help you to become more accurate in English without having to learn grammar rules. With lots of practice, you will begin to remember chunks of words and phrases. This helps in remembering word patterns in a sentence and how certain words go with others.

5. Practice

Regular and consistent practice is the key to success when it comes to speaking English. The tips and suggestions that we've described above only work if you use them regularly. So, here's what we recommend. Start small – spend just 10 minutes every day doing 1-2 of the above things. Maybe listen to a short video clip today and imitate. Reflect on what you learned. Tomorrow, pick up a short article. Read aloud and summarize in your own words. Reflect on what you read and the new words. Do not forget to have fun. It's easier to learn something new and commit to learning when you're having fun. Practice English by singing along to popular songs. Practice tongue twisters with your friends.

In conclusion, speech is an effective skill and one of the four skills that are very important in learning English. Speech is very helpful in bringing people face to face with their lives. Speaking is the process of sending and receiving a message or information. These strategies are good to use in teaching speech.

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